

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D1.12 REPORT ON KEY COMMUNICATION EVENTS - 3RD REPORTING PERIOD

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1. INTRODUCTION

Dissemination and Communication (D&C) activities have been integral to the project from its outset, supporting the maximization of its impact by reaching a broad audience and promoting the uptake of results. This Deliverable D1.12, “Report on Key Communication Events – 3rd Reporting Period,” presents the strategies and outcomes of the communication activities carried out during the third reporting period of the project (M31–M48, 01/11/2024–30/04/2026). As this reporting period coincides with the conclusion of the project, the report also provides, where relevant, a consolidated overview of the overall results achieved across its full duration, in order to offer a more comprehensive perspective on the project's impact and communication efforts. These activities build upon the roadmap established in Deliverable D1.4, “Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan,” which defines the target audiences, tools, and events for effective dissemination. The plan was regularly updated to remain aligned with ongoing project developments. Progress on D&C activities, initially reported in D1.5, “Annual Report on Key Communication Events,” was further updated in this deliverable and was monitored through to the final reporting stage at M48, together with the update on the dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan (Deliverable D1.16). The project virtual galleries of marine annelids are described in detail in the deliverable D1.10, “Report on Virtual galleries of the Voucher Specimens Collection”, while the dedicated workshops are presented in the deliverable D1.13, “Final Report on MAPWORMS Workshops”.

An overview of the Consortium's communication activities is provided in the tables included throughout this report. All partners actively contributed to enhancing the project's visibility and supporting the dissemination of results to public, scientific, technical, and industrial audiences. These efforts ensure a balanced representation of all disciplines involved in the project, including biology, soft robotics, chemistry, smart hydrogels, and mathematical modelling. This collective engagement has been instrumental in maintaining a comprehensive and up-to-date record of project outputs across the relevant fields.

1.1 MAPWORMS DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

The dissemination and communication (D&C) activities of the MAPWORMS project are designed to share research outcomes and pilot experiences across Europe and internationally. The Consortium placed strong emphasis on fostering interest in research and entrepreneurship among younger generations, with the aim of demonstrating how education and careers in science and engineering can contribute positively to society. In this context, MAPWORMS actively engages in outreach activities targeting students and the general public, including science fairs, educational workshops, and interactive sessions, which highlight the societal relevance of scientific and technological innovation.

In parallel, the project maintained a strong presence within the scientific and industrial communities through active participation in international conferences, industrial forums,

and specialized workshops. These activities facilitated knowledge exchange, strengthen engagement with academic and industrial stakeholders, and enhanced the visibility of MAPWORMS within relevant expert networks.

From the outset of the project, dedicated D&C channels have been established, with a strong focus on digital tools. Recognizing the central role of digital communication in reaching diverse audiences, MAPWORMS has invested significant effort in developing and maintaining its website and social media platforms. These channels served not only to disseminate project results, but also to foster a multidisciplinary community encompassing all major project domains.

To ensure coordinated planning, continuous monitoring, and systematic improvement of D&C activities, the MAPWORMS Consortium organized regular online meetings. As of this third reporting period, a total of 44 monthly Consortium meetings has been held, including 26 meetings reported in previous periods and an additional 18 meetings covered in the present update (Figure 1). These meetings played a central role in aligning dissemination strategies, supervising ongoing activities, and adapting communication efforts in response to project progress and emerging opportunities.

Figure 1. Print screen of one of the online monthly meetings.

In the following sections, we present a structured overview of the Consortium's dissemination and communication activities. This includes a detailed assessment of the performance of the project's social media channels and website, with a focus on engagement indicators and audience growth. The sections also summarize the

Consortium's participation in outreach activities targeting the general public, as well as its involvement in conferences and forums within the scientific and industrial communities. Finally, a comprehensive overview of the publications produced by the Consortium is provided, highlighting ongoing efforts to disseminate research outcomes through academic journals and other relevant platforms.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

2.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project website was developed at the beginning of the MAPWORMS project by the Project Coordinator, SSSA, with contributions from the entire Consortium, and was launched in July 2022. Since then, it has served as the central communication hub and primary front-end for engaging with the project's diverse target audiences. Hosted and maintained by SSSA, the website functions as a key point of interaction, providing comprehensive and up-to-date information on the project's objectives, progress, achievements, and scientific outcomes. It offers easy access to a wide range of dissemination materials, including project results, research findings, multimedia content, public presentations, and information on upcoming events. Through the website, MAPWORMS facilitates effective sharing of project activities and results, while data dissemination and sharing practices are implemented in accordance with the FAIR Data Principles and the project's Data Management Plan.

SEO (Search Engine Optimization) strategies have been integrated into the MAPWORMS website since its launch to enhance its visibility, improve search engine ranking, and drive organic traffic. Indeed, these efforts facilitate the discovery of the website through relevant keywords aligned with the project's core research areas, such as "robotics", "bioinspiration", "untethered actuation" "smart materials", "smart technologies", "marine annelids", and "shape-morphing behaviour". The overall design and structure of the website reflect the MAPWORMS objective of demonstrating how science and engineering research can generate positive societal impact.

Website performance, user behaviour, and traffic statistics have been continuously monitored since July 2022 using the WP Statistics – WordPress tool, providing quantitative insights that support the ongoing optimization of content and user engagement.

NUMBER OF VISITS AND VISITORS

Over the entire course of the project, the MAPWORMS website attracted a total of **16283** visitors, representing individual users who accessed the platform, and recorded **38476** total visits, indicating repeated engagement with project content over time. The highest level of user activity was observed in September 2025, reflecting a period of increased interest and interaction. Figure 2 illustrates the evolution of both unique visitors and total visits throughout

the entire project, with particular emphasis on the third reporting period, highlighting the overall growth and continued engagement with the website.

Figure 2. MAPWORMS website visitors and visits throughout the entire project, highlighting the third reporting period (November 2024 to April 2026) (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

The audience of the MAPWORMS website is geographically diverse, with visitors originating from multiple regions worldwide. The United States, China, and Italy consistently account for the highest share of website traffic in the 3rd reporting period. A detailed distribution of visitors across the top 15 countries is shown in Figure 3, highlighting the international reach of the MAPWORMS digital presence.

Rank	Flag	Country	Visitor Count
1		United States	6,741
2		China	1,472
3		Italy	963
4		United Kingdom	952
5		Germany	928
6		Singapore	798
7		Hong Kong	573
8		Russian Federation	525
9		France	441
10		Viet Nam	412
11		Sweden	397
12		India	378
13		Brazil	366
14		Netherlands	315
15		Australia	239
16		Canada	238
17		Ireland	221
18		Austria	164
19		Greece	157
20		Belgium	144

Figure 3. Visitors' Demographics distribution (3rd reporting period: November 2024 to April 2026) (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

PAGE VIEWS

During the reporting period, the most frequently visited pages on the MAPWORMS website were the “Contact” and “News & Events” pages, reflecting strong user interest in learning about the project, the participating organizations, and potential points of contact with the Consortium. This pattern indicates that visitors are not only consuming project-related information but are also actively seeking opportunities to engage further with the Consortium and its partners.

As shown in Figure 4, the top ten most-visited pages provide additional insight into user behaviour, revealing sustained interest across multiple sections of the website, including regularly updated news and posts. These usage patterns help identify which content areas

are most effective in attracting user attention and inform the ongoing refinement of website content and structure to enhance engagement.

▲ Top Pages

ID	Title	Link	Visits
1	Contact	/contact/	1,512
2	News & Events	/news-events/	1,323
3	Vexlum	/vexlum/	1,033
4	MAPWORMS at the 83rd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union and the 57th European Marine Biology Symposium	/2024/10/06/mapworms-at-the-83rd-congress-of-the-italian-zoological-union-and-the-57th-european-marine-biology-symposium/	997
5	information data protection	/information-data-protection	933
6	Project	/project-1/	862
7	MAPWORMS at the European Robotics Forum 2025: Workshop, Booth, and Future Visions for Soft Robotics	/2025/04/16/mapworms-at-the-erf2025/	836
8	SSSA	/sssa/	830
9	HUJI	/huji/	638
10	Results	/results/	611

Figure 4. MAPWORMS page views (3rd reporting period: November 2024 to April 2026) (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

Monitoring page-level traffic is a key element of the overall website strategy, supporting the optimization of information accessibility and user experience. This continuous analysis enables the MAPWORMS team to adapt and improve the website over time, ensuring effective dissemination of project information and maintaining a strong digital presence.

2.2 SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS

MAPWORMS has maintained an active presence on key social media platforms, primarily LinkedIn® and Facebook®, which were established during the early months of the project and have been continuously updated throughout its duration. While a Twitter® account was initially created at the project's outset, subsequent monitoring indicated limited engagement on this platform. As a result, dissemination efforts were strategically consolidated on LinkedIn and Facebook, where more active scientific, professional, and technology-oriented communities aligned closely with the MAPWORMS research theme. Monitoring of the people interaction with these social media was a useful indicator of the achieved interest (Table 1).

Table 1. Analysis of the metrics on Social Media Networks

	1 st reporting period: July. 2022 to Oct. 2022	2 nd reporting period: Nov. 2021 to Oct. 2024	3 rd reporting period: Nov. 2024 to Apr. 2026
Post reach	185	977	1160
Post engagement	286	99	97
Reactions	39	50	48
Photo views	165	18	117

The selection and continued use of these platforms are based on their effectiveness in supporting the project's communication objectives. In particular, they enable engagement with targeted audiences interested in science, engineering, and innovation, facilitate dialogue that extends beyond the academic community to the general public, and increase overall visibility of MAPWORMS and its multidisciplinary research activities. To support these goals, communications adopt an accessible and friendly tone, aimed at conveying scientific content in a clear and engaging manner.

The performance of MAPWORMS social media activities has been continuously monitored using the analytics tools provided by each platform. Metrics related to reach, engagement, and audience interaction have been regularly reviewed to assess the effectiveness of communication strategies and to inform ongoing adjustments aimed at maximizing impact and visibility.

LINKEDIN

Over the course of the project, the MAPWORMS LinkedIn account has shown sustained growth and engagement, reaching a total of **734** followers to date. Content has been shared on a regular basis, with an average posting frequency of approximately one post per week, resulting in around 30 posts over the most recent 365-day period. These posts have consistently communicated project milestones, technological developments, and overall progress, effectively engaging the scientific and professional communities relevant to MAPWORMS. Throughout the reporting period, MAPWORMS has maintained consistent interaction with its LinkedIn audience. As illustrated in Figure 5 and Figure 6, posts generated a variety of reactions, including likes, comments, and shares, demonstrating a high level of audience engagement over the past 365 days. These interactions reflect sustained interest in MAPWORMS activities and research outcomes and have contributed to the development of an active professional network around the project.

Figure 5. Monthly aggregate reactions to MAPWORMS LinkedIn posts over the past 365 days. Red stars indicate the dates when posts had the highest number of reactions.

Figure 6. Number of organics impression (left) and clicks (right) on MAPWORMS LinkedIn posts over the past 365 days.

Several posts achieved particularly high visibility and engagement. The most widely viewed post highlighted the presentation of MAPWORMS results at the booth, held during the European Robotics Forum (ERF 2025) in Stuttgart on 25 March 2025, reaching 1,652 organic impressions. The second most-viewed post, with 1,644 organic impressions, featured the 3rd Annual Meeting of the European MAPWORMS Project in Lecce, Italy, underlining strong interest in the project's technological innovations.

FACEBOOK

As of the current reporting period, the MAPWORMS Facebook page has built a stable and growing audience, reaching 218 followers to date. Engagement with published content has remained consistent, with a post reach of 643 recorded over the most recent 28-day period. A detailed overview of key performance metrics for the Facebook page during this period is provided in Table 2, offering insight into recent audience interaction and visibility.

On average, content has been published on the MAPWORMS Facebook page approximately once per two weeks, ensuring a regular flow of project-related information and updates. Over the most recent 12-month period, a total of 29 posts were published, covering topics such as project milestones, research highlights, and upcoming events.

Among these, the highest-performing post in the past 90 days was published on 5 February 2026 and featured the scientific paper delivered by CoNISMa, which explored the rich diversity of marine annelids from the Salento Peninsula. The post reached 1,160 impressions and generated 48 reactions, indicating strong audience interest in the project's activities and outreach efforts.

Through regular updates and targeted communication efforts, the MAPWORMS Facebook page continues to serve as an effective platform for enhancing project visibility and fostering engagement with a broad audience, including both the scientific community and the general public.

Table 2. Key metrics related to the MAPWORMS Facebook page during the period from 1 January 2025 to 28 April 2026.

Metrics	Number
Post reach	13407
Post engagement	520
Reactions	250

3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATIONS ACTIVITIES

3.1 PUBLICATIONS

The publications produced by the MAPWORMS Consortium over the course of the project are summarized in Table 3, where those published during the third reporting period are highlighted in red.

Throughout the project duration, all partners have actively worked to align with best practices in Open Science. Whenever possible, the Consortium has pursued Gold Open Access publishing, ensuring that MAPWORMS research outputs are freely and immediately accessible to the international scientific community. This approach supports broad dissemination and maximizes the visibility and impact of the research generated within the project.

In cases where Gold Open Access is not available, such as certain conference proceedings or abstracts, the Consortium has adopted a Green Open Access approach. This allows authors to make pre-print versions of their work openly available, ensuring continued access to research results. In addition, all scientific outputs and dissemination materials are systematically archived in institutional or public repositories. In particular, a dedicated community on Zenodo (EU Open Research Repository), titled "MAPWORMS COMMUNITY", has been established to host pre-prints, presentations, posters, public deliverables, and related materials. Together, these practices ensure long-term accessibility of MAPWORMS outputs and contribute to the broader goals of open and transparent scientific research.

Table 3. MAPWORMS Publications M1-M48. Publications produced during the third reporting period (M31-M48) are highlighted in red.

Author	Title	Journal/conference	Type	Status	Date	DOI / Link	Open Access	Comments
CoNISMa	Marine annelids as models for innovative robots	81 st Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	Poster	Presented	Sep. 2022	DOI	yes	
SSSA	A Bioinspired Fluid-Filled Soft Linear Actuator	Soft Robotics Journal	Journal	Published	Nov. 2022	DOI	yes	
SSSA	Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS: the MAPWORMS Project	European Robotics Forum (ERF 2023)	Poster	Presented	Mar. 2023		no	The poster was presented during the ERF Forum but not published
HCMR	Scientific community needs: FAIR and credible data repositories. The case of MedOBIS	International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)	Poster	Published	Mar. 2023	Link DOI	yes	The conference titled "The data we need for the Ocean we want" took place at the UNESCO Headquarters in Paris

	Repository and MAPWORMS Project							
SSSA	Mechanics of tubular meshes made of helical fibers and application to modeling McKibben artificial muscles	6th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2023)	Poster	Presented	Apr. 2023	DOI	yes	
HUJI	Stimuli-Responsive DNA-Based Hydrogels on Surfaces for Switchable Bioelectrocatalysis and Controlled Release of Loads	Applied Materials and Interfaces	Journal	Published	Jul. 2023	DOI	yes	
CoNISM a	Towards a new standard for marine annelid checklists: the Salento Peninsula as a case study	82 nd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	Poster	Presented	Sep. 2023	DOI	yes	
CoNISM a	Biodiversity patterns in marine annelids associated to intertidal coralline algae along the Salento Peninsula	14 th National Conference on Biodiversity/1 st International Conference on Mediterranean Biodiversity	Poster	Presented	Sep. 2023	DOI	yes	
HUJI	Stiffness-Switchable Biocatalytic pH-Responsive DNA-Functionalized Polyacrylamide Cryogels and Their Mechanical Applications	Advanced Functional Materials	Journal	Published	Oct. 2023	DOI	yes	
HUJI	Chemical and Photochemical-Driven Dissipative Fe ³⁺ /Fe ²⁺ -Ion Cross-Linked Carboxymethyl Cellulose Gels Operating Under Aerobic Conditions: Applications for Transient Controlled Release and Mechanical Actuation	Journal of the American Chemical Society JACS	Journal	Published	Mar. 2024	DOI	yes	

CoNISM a	Non-indigenous polychaetes along the Salento Peninsula: new records and first molecular data	Mediterranean Marine Science	Journal	Published	Apr. 2024	DOI	yes	
HCMR	Applying Fair principles to micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS project	5th International Congress on Applied Ichthyology, Oceanography, and Aquatic Environment (HydroMediT 2024)	Presentations	Presented	May - June 2024	Link DOI	yes	
CoNISM a	Biological and functional diversity of marine annelids as inspiration for innovative soft robots	57th European Marine Biology Symposium	Presentations	Presented	Sep 2024		no	The work was presented during the conference, but the book of abstracts was not made public.
CoNISM a	The sipunculan <i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> (Annelida: Phascolosomatidae) as a new model for bioinspired robots	83rd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	Presentations	Presented	Sep 2024	Link	yes	The book of abstracts is uploaded here: https://www.uzionlus.it/83-congresso-uzi-2024/book-of-abstract.html
VELLUM	Progress of turnkey VECSEL systems for quantum technology	Turnkey VECSEL systems for quantum technology	Proceedings	Published	Mar 2025	DOI	yes	
SSSA	Worm-Inspired Soft Robot with Magnetically Driven Eversible Proboscis	European Robotics Forum (ERF 2025)	Poster		Mar 2025	DOI	yes	
SSSA	Worm-Inspired Soft Robot with Magnetically Driven Eversible Proboscis	8th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2025)	Poster		Apr 2025		yes	The Poster was extracted from the paper "Magnetically-Driven Deployable Structure Inspired by Worms"
SSSA	Worm-Inspired Soft Robot with Magnetically Driven Eversible Proboscis	workshop "Nature Inspired Intelligence: Biomimetic and Hybrid Materials for Autonomous Soft Machines" at RoboSoft25	Poster		Apr 2025	Link	yes	The Poster was extracted from the paper "Magnetically-Driven Deployable Structure Inspired by Worms"
CoNISM a	Integrated checklist of marine annelids along the	The LifeWatch ERIC Biodiversity &	Presentations	Presented	Jul 2025	Link	yes	The book of abstracts is uploaded here: LifeWatch ERIC. (2025). The LifeWatch

	Salento Peninsula unravels gaps of knowledge in their diversity and distribution	Ecosystem eScience Conference (Bees 2025)	Proceedings						ERIC Biodiversity and Ecosystem eScience Conference (BEES) 2025 – Book of Abstracts. LifeWatch ERIC. https://doi.org/10.48372/OXWH-3K26
CoNISMa	Reconstruction of the functional anatomy of <i>Phascolosoma stephensi</i> Stephen, 1942 (Annelida: Sipuncula: Phascolosomatidae) through micro-CT	The LifeWatch ERIC Biodiversity & Ecosystem eScience Conference (Bees 2025)	Presentation- Proceedings	Presented	Jul 2025	Link	yes		The book of abstracts is uploaded here: LifeWatch ERIC. (2025). The LifeWatch ERIC Biodiversity and Ecosystem eScience Conference (BEES) 2025 – Book of Abstracts. LifeWatch ERIC. https://doi.org/10.48372/OXWH-3K26
HCMR	Micro-CT: A useful tool for exploring the pharyngeal movement in polychaetes	The LifeWatch ERIC Biodiversity & Ecosystem eScience Conference (Bees 2025)	Poster	Presented	Jul 2025	Link	yes		The book of abstracts is uploaded here: LifeWatch ERIC. (2025). The LifeWatch ERIC Biodiversity and Ecosystem eScience Conference (BEES) 2025 – Book of Abstracts. LifeWatch ERIC. https://doi.org/10.48372/OXWH-3K26
CoNISMa	First record of the non-indigenous <i>Myrianida pachycera</i> (Augener, 1913) (Annelida: Syllidae) in the Mediterranean Sea revealed by integrative taxonomy	BioInvasions Records	Journal	Published	Aug 2025	DOI	yes		
HCMR	"Η ανατομία των θαλάσσιων σκωλήκων ως έμπνευση για τη ρομποτική"	"Κρήτη και Θάλασσα" an event organised by HCMR and FORTH	Poster	Presented	Feb 2026	Link DOI	yes		The title of the poster in English was "the anatomy of marine worms as inspiration for robotics"
CoNISMa	Bridging past and present: the Salento Peninsula as a case study for unveiling marine annelid diversity by integrating literature, field surveys, and DNA barcoding	The European Zoological Journal	Journal	Published	Feb 2026	DOI	yes		
HCMR, CoNISMa	Functional anatomy of the pharynx of <i>Glycera tridactyla</i> Schmarda, 1861	Journal of Morphology	Journal	Submitted	Feb 2026		yes		In case of acceptance it will be published as an open access

	(Annelida: Glyceriformia: Glyceridae)							
SSSA, CoNISMa, HCMR	Unsegmented Marine Annelids as Biomechanical Models for Soft Robotics	Scientific Reports	Journal	Published	Mar 2026	DOI	yes	
SSSA	Small-scale magnetic peristaltic soft robot with mobility and transport capabilities	Submitted to Advanced Intelligent Systems	Journal	Submitted to review	Mar 2026		Undergoing	
SSSA	Reconfigurable Soft Magnetic Architectures for Deployable Morphing Structures	9th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2026)	Presentation - Proceedings		Apr 2026		yes	
SSSA	Magnetically-Driven Deployable Structure Inspired by Worms	9th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2026)	Poster		Apr 2026	Link	yes	The Poster was extracted from the paper
CoNISMa	To be or not to be alien, that is the question: the case of five new polychaete species from the Levantine Sea	Mediterranean Marine Science	Journal	Accepted	Apr 2026		Undergoing	
SSSA	Magnetically-Driven Deployable Structure Inspired by Worms	Bioinspiration & Biomimetics	Journal	Accepted	Apr 2026		yes	

3.2 PRESS RELEASES

The press releases issued by the MAPWORMS Consortium over the entire course of the project are summarized in Table 4 with the press releases published during the third reporting period (M31–M48) highlighted in red. These press releases have played an important role in communicating key project developments and achievements to a broad audience, including the general public, relevant stakeholders, and the scientific community. Through the regular dissemination of timely and well-structured press materials, the Consortium has enhanced the visibility of MAPWORMS and increased awareness of its objectives, progress, and innovative outcomes.

Table 4. MAPWORMS Press Releases M1-M48. Press releases published during the third reporting period (M31–M48) are highlighted in red.

Author	Title	Magazine	Type	Status	Date	DOI/ Link	Open Access	Comments
SSSA	The interaction between biology and engineering develops new bio-inspired robotic solutions in the medical field and for marine monitoring. MAPWORMS, coordinated by the BioRobotics Institute, is the new project funded by European Commission	Sant'Anna Magazine	Press release	Published	May 2022	Link	Yes	
HCMR	MAPWORMS: Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in worms	Cretalive news	Press release	Published	Dec. 2022	Link	Yes	This press release is in Greek
SSSA	Una nuova generazione di robot si prende cura degli uomini (a new robot generation takes care of humans)	Class	Press release	Published	Feb. 2023	Link	No	This press release is in Italian
HCMR	News on LifeWatch ERIC: Bioinspired robots in Lecce: MAPWORMS Plenary meeting	LifeWatch ERIC news	Press release	Published	May 2023	Link	Yes	
CoNISMa	Robot ispirati ai vermi marini: l'idea in un progetto di ricerca italiano	Kodami	Press release	Published	Aug. 2023	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNISMa	Mapworms: progetto di ricerca italiano sviluppa robot ispirati a vermi marini	Lega Nerd	Press release	Published	Aug. 2023	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNISMa	Mapworms, l'affascinante progetto italiano dei robot vermi	DigiTech.News	Press release	Published	Aug. 2023	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNISMa	Vermi robot, nuova frontiera in soccorso alla vita umana	Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno	Press release	Published	Oct. 2023	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNISMa	Vermi robot iniettati nel corpo per operazioni oggi impossibili: nasce il prototipo ispirato a organismi presenti nei mari pugliesi	La Repubblica	Press release	Published	Oct. 2023	Link	No	Press release in Italian
HCMR	Τα σκουλήκια εμπνέουν τους επιστήμονες, γίνονται ρομπότ και το δεξί χέρι ενός χειρουργού!	Cretalive news	Press release	Published	May 2024	Link	Yes	This press release is in Greek
CoNISMa	Dal verme marino al robot medico: UniSalento apre la strada alla chirurgia del futuro VIDEO	La Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno	Press release	Published	March 2026	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNISMa	UniSalento: un verme robot per la medicina del futuro	TeleRamaNews.it	Press release	Published	April 2026	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian

CoNISMa	Il verme robot per la medicina: un progetto UniSalento	UnoGenio	Press release	Published	April 2026	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNISMa, HCMR, SSSA,	Il microrobot che sembra un verme	Buongiorno Regione	Press release	Published	April 2026	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian
CoNISMa	BIO-ROBOT DAL MARE	TGR Leonardo	Press release	Published	April 2026	Link	Yes	Press release in Italian

3.3 EVENTS

MAPWORMS partners have carried out extensive dissemination activities through participation in a wide range of events spanning multiple disciplines, including robotics, biology, chemistry, smart materials, and mathematical modelling (Table 5). A strong presence at international scientific conferences has enabled the Consortium to effectively communicate research results to expert audiences closely aligned with the project's scientific scope. These venues provided opportunities to showcase advanced developments emerging from MAPWORMS, exchange knowledge with peers, and initiate or strengthen collaborations within the academic research community (Figure 7).

Figure 7. (A) People attending the presentation of the MAPWORMS project at ERF 2025 and (B) ERF 2026. People from presenting the MAPWORMS project general Meeting at (C) Lecce (2025) and (D) Pisa (2026).

Engagement with industrial stakeholders has represented another important component of the project's dissemination strategy. All partners, and in particular the industrial partners ACMIT and VEXLUM, have actively promoted MAPWORMS within their professional networks. For example, ACMIT has presented the project to its existing and prospective industrial partners, reaching approximately 60 companies worldwide and engaging around 100 individuals per year, thereby strengthening the project's visibility within relevant industrial ecosystems.

Under the MAPWORMS project, two exhibitions were also held at the Marine Biology Museum “Pietro Parenzan” of the University of Salento (Porto Cesareo, Italy), on its reopening (18 December 2024), and at the Cretaquarium, as part of HCMR (Gournes, Greece) on International Polychaete Day 2025 (01 July 2025). On these occasions, the model organisms, as well as the rationale and progress of the MAPWORMS project were presented to the general public (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Activities and leaflet from the exhibition held at Cretaquarium during International Polychaete Day.

To support and enhance these dissemination activities, a range of communication materials has been developed throughout the project. These include leaflets, videos, and promotional items designed to convey key project messages in an accessible format. From the early stages of MAPWORMS, printed leaflets have been distributed at conferences, workshops, and public events, providing concise information on project objectives, Consortium composition, and main outcomes. When more in-depth communication was required, posters were used to visually present the project's goals and results, further reinforcing dissemination and outreach efforts. Details about the communication materials

can be found in the deliverable D1.16 (Updated Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan).

Table 5. MAPWORMS events M1-M48. Events taking place during the third reporting period (M31–M48) are highlighted in red.

Name	Date	Location	Type	Status	Partner	Contribution (organize/participate)	Size audience	Web site	Comments
DNA-Nanotechnology	12-14 May 2022	Germany	Conference	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Stimuli-Responsive DNA-based hydrogels And Their Applications	80	Link	
Scuola di Orientamento Universitario – 2022 at SSSA	23 June 2022	Pisa (Italy)	Presentation	Presentation for young students	SSSA		>50	Link	
Festival del pensare	24 July 2022	Montescudaio, Italy	Festival	Participated as invited speaker	SSSA	Workshop "Il mio amico robot"	>200	Link	Festival for general public
Prof alla Torre!	04 August 2022	Porto Cesareo, Italy	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project through the conference "Vermi marini robot"	>50	Link	"Prof. alla Torre!" is the annual dissemination festival organised by the Marine Biology Museum of the University of Salento, aimed at introducing the marine biological research carried out at the University of Salento to the general public.
81 st Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	20-23 September 2022	Trieste, Italy	Conference	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated with the poster "Marine annelids as models for innovative robots"	>200	Link	
MINERVA Center for Biohybrid Materials School	6-11 November 2022	Israel	MINERVA School conference	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Stimuli-Responsive Hydrogels for Nanomedicine, Self-Healing and Mechanical Applications	90		
G-quadruplex Webinar	19 January 2023	Virtual	Webinar	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: G-Quadruplex Responsive Hydrogels and	200		

						Interphases, and Their Applications			
European Robotics Forum (ERF 2023)	14 – 16 March 2023	Odense, Denmark	Forum	Participated with poster	SSSA	Poster "Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS: the MAPWORMS Project"	>1000	Link	
International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)	20-21 March 2023	Paris, France	Conference	Participated	HCMR	Participate though the poster titled "Scientific community needs: FAIR and credible data repositories. The case of MedOBIS Repository and MAPWORMS Project"	>300	Link	International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)
6th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2023)	3-7 April 2023	Singapore	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Participated with poster titled "Mechanics of tubular meshes made of helical fibers and application to modeling McKibben artificial muscles"	>2000	Link	
2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)	29 May – 2 June 2023	London (UK)	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Invited speaker at "Soft Robotics: Fusing function with structure" workshop	>500	Link	
Prof alla Torre!	01 July – 10 August 2023	Porto Cesareo	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the results of the first year of the MAPWORMS project	>50	Link	Dissemination festival
Living Machines 2023	10-13 July 2023	Genoa (Italy)	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Organizer of "worm-inspired machines" workshop	>1000	Link	
I mercoledì della biologia marina	05 July – 03 August 2023	San Foca (Italy)	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project	>50	Link	Dissemination festival
Invited Lecture	08 August 2023	East China University for Science and Technology	Presentation	Participated	HUJI	Invited Lecture: Dynamic hydrogel and Cryogel Materials and Their Applications	200		
14 th National Conference on Biodiversity/1 st International Conference on Mediterranean Biodiversity	13-15 September 2023	Lecce (Italy)	Conference	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated with the poster "Biodiversity patterns in marine annelids associated to intertidal coralline algae along the Salento Peninsula"	>150	Link	

82nd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	19-22 September 2023	Palermo (Italy)	Conference	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated with the poster "Towards a new standard for marine annelid checklists: the Salento Peninsula as a case study"	>200	Link	
Lecce Fantafest	25-27 September 2023	Lecce (Italy)	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated to a round table on innovative technologies	>100	Link	Cineforum on science fiction movies with a round table of academic experts
2 nd Congress Online on Marine Evolution	14-17 November 2023	Online event	Conference	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of some taxonomic results obtained in the context of the MAPWORMS project	>70	Link	
Innodays 2023	24-26 November 2023	Crete (Greece)	Exhibition	Participated	HCMR	Micro-CT scans were presented through a touchscreen monitor	>5000	Link	On the Mediterranean Agri-Food Competence Centre (MACC) stand, A touchscreen monitor was installed and the MAPWORMS micro-CT scans were displayed and the visitors could interactively manipulate them
European Robotics Forum (2024)	13-15 March 2024	Rimini (Italy)	Forum	Participated	SSSA, ACMIT	Organizer of "Translational challenges of soft robotics in medical applications" workshop	>300	Link	
7th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2024)	14 April 2024	San Diego (USA)	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project to the audience	>2000	Link	
The 18 th International Symposium on Macrocyclic and Supramolecular Chemistry	06-10 May 2024	Hangzhou China	Conference	Participated	HUJI	Plenary lecture: Stimuli-Responsive Supramolecular Oligonucleotide Systems: From Functional Materials to Protocells	400	Link	
DNA Nanotechnology 2024 Meeting	23-25-May 2024	Jena, Germany	Conference	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Dynamic Dissipative, Transient DNA-Networks and	60	link	

						Nanostructures from Basic Concepts to Applications			
Pisa Robotics Festival 2024	26 May 2024	Pisa, Italy	Workshop	Participated with poster and a talk.	SSSA	Co-organizer of Workshop titled "Medical Robotics Workshop"	>50	Link	
5th International Congress on Applied Ichthyology, Oceanography, and Aquatic Environment (HydroMediT 2024)	30 May-2 June 2024	Mytilene (Greece)	Conference	Participated with presentation	HCMR	Presentation titled "Applying fair principles to micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS project"	>300	Link	
The Hamlyn Symposium on Medical Robotics	25 June 2024	London (UK)	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Presentation the MAPWORMS project to the audience	>500	Link	
Oceanitalians	26 June 2024	Online event	Roundtable	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation the MAPWORMS project to the audience of the Oceanitalian facebook page	>100	Link .	Dissemination online event also posted on the Youtube page of Oceanitalians
The 11 th International Translational Conference on DNA-Nanotechnology	06-08 July 2024	Chengdu China	Conference	Participated	HUJI	Plenary Lecture: Stimuli-Responsive Materials and Their Applications	200	Link	
Invited Lecture	10 July 2024	Wuhan University, China	Presentation	Participated	HUJI	Invited Lecture: Dynamic Stimuli-Responsive Nanostructures, Materials, and Circuitries and Their Applications	150		
Award Lecture	04 Sept. 2024	San Sebastian, Spain	Presentation	Participated	HUJI	Invited Award Lecture: Dynamic Nucleic Acid Nanostructures and Systems: From fundamental Concepts to Applications	100		
83rd Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	11-14 September 2024	Pisa (Italy)	Conference	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the results of the first two years of the MAPWORMS project	>250	Link	
57 th European Marine Biology Symposium	16-20 September 2024	Naples (Italy)	Conference	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the results of the first two years of the MAPWORMS project	>250	Link	

Bright Night 2024	27 September 2024	Pisa, Italy	Exhibition	Participated	SSSA	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project to the general public	>250	Link	
International Nanomaterials Symposium	31-Oct to 2-Nov-2024	Suzhu, China	Conference	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Dynamic Nucleic Acid Nanostructures and Systems: From	200		
European Robotics Forum (ERF 2025)	25-27-March 2025	Stuttgart, Germany	Forum	Participated	SSSA, ACMIT	Organisation of "Bringing Soft Robotics to Application" Workshop	>300	Link	
The LifeWatch ERIC Biodiversity & Ecosystem eScience Conference (Bees 2025)	30 June – 3 July 2025	Heraklion, Crete	Conference	Participated with poster	HCMR	Participated with the poster " Micro-CT: A useful tool for exploring the pharyngeal movement in polychaetes"	193	Link	
International Polychaete Day	1 July 2025	Cretaquarium, Heraklion, Crete	Festival	Organiser	HCMR	HCMR organised a festival at Cretaquarium for International Polychaete Day, where the general public explored marine worms through a variety of activities.	100	Link	
The Twentieth International Symposium on Electroanalytical Chemistry	12-15 Aug-2025	Changhun, China	Conference	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Stimuli-Responsive Dynamic Electrochemical Systems	300	Link	
84th Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	16-19 September 2025	Cagliari, Italy	Conference	Participated with poster	CoNISMa	CoNISMa participated with the poster "Functional anatomy of the eversible pharynx of Glycera tridactyla (Annelida: Glyceridae): A micro-CT contribution"		Link	
"Κρήτη και Θάλασσα"	10 February 2026	Heraklion, Crete	Event	Participated with poster	HCMR	HCMR participated with the poster " Η ανατομία των θαλάσσιων σκωλήκων ως έμπνευση για τη ρομποτική"	100	Link	
Micro-CT tour for students through HCMR educational unit	Nov 2024-March 2026	Heraklion, Crete	Tour	Organiser	HCMR	Presentation of MAPWORMS activities to primary and secondary school students visiting the HCMR bioimaging lab	>150		

European Robotics Forum (ERF 2026)	23-27-March 2026	Stavnger, Norway	Forum	Participated	SSSA, ACMIT	Organisation of "Bringing Soft Robotics to Application" Workshop	>300	link	
Austrian Long Night of Research 2026	24 April 2026	Wiener Neustadt, Austria	Research results presentation for the public	Participated	ACMIT	Poster, oral presentation of the MAPWORMS project	2600+	Link	

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provided a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and communication activities carried out throughout the 18-month duration of the MAPWORMS project (M31–M48, 01/11/2024–30/04/2026), corresponding to the third reporting period. As this marked the end of the project, the document placed particular emphasis on both the overall results achieved across the entire project and those obtained specifically during this reporting period. It documents the use of digital tools, scientific publications, events, and outreach initiatives, including participation in international conferences, regular updates on the MAPWORMS website, and targeted communication actions on social media platforms, primarily LinkedIn and Facebook.

4.1 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS – THIRD REPORTING PERIOD

Key performance indicators (KPIs) were systematically employed to monitor progress and assess the effectiveness of these activities. The consortium published two papers and submitted five additional manuscripts to high-impact journals. During the third reporting period (M31–M48), the project website attracted 24.963 visits. LinkedIn gained 756 followers, while Facebook gained 218 followers.

4.2 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS – OVERALL PROJECT

The analysis presented in this deliverable D1.12 "Report on Key Communication Events – 3rd Reporting Period" considered both the activities carried out during the third reporting period (M31–M48) and the cumulative KPIs over the entire project duration (M1–M48), in order to provide a comprehensive assessment of the project's dissemination and communication performance at its conclusion.

Overall, the consortium demonstrated a strong performance with respect to the targets defined in the proposal (Figure 9. Target KPIs for dissemination and communication activities as defined in the project proposal, including expected growth trends across the project duration (M1–M48).Figure 9), achieving or closely approaching most of the expected outcomes. The scientific dissemination activity was particularly solid, with a total of 8 peer-reviewed

publications produced and 4 additional manuscripts submitted to high-impact journals, reflecting the quality and relevance of the research carried out within the project.

Figure 9. Target KPIs for dissemination and communication activities as defined in the project proposal, including expected growth trends across the project duration (M1-M48).

In terms of online visibility and outreach, the project website recorded 43,255 visits over the full project duration, closely aligning with the expected growth outlined in the proposal, which projected approximately 45,000 visits by the final stage. Social media channels also showed consistent and positive engagement trends: LinkedIn reached 756 followers and Facebook 218 followers, exceeding the indicative milestones presented in the proposal (e.g., around 300 followers by the end of the project), and confirming the effectiveness of the communication strategy in engaging relevant audiences.

Additionally, the wide range of dissemination and communication activities implemented throughout the project—including publications, events, and digital outreach—contributed to strengthening the project's visibility and impact within both the scientific community and the broader public.

Taken together, these results demonstrate that the large majority of the communication and dissemination objectives set at proposal stage were successfully achieved, and in several cases exceeded, by the end of the project, highlighting the overall effectiveness of the strategy adopted by the consortium.